

Behaviour of Nitrophenols with *p*-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride. Part II.

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It was shown by one of us (Sane and Joshi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2481) that OH group in nitrophenols, excepting 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresol* which gives ester, is replaced by chlorine by means of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in presence of diethylaniline if there are two nitro groups present in *ortho* and *para* positions respectively to OH, but if sodium carbonate is used instead of diethylaniline, toluenesulphonyl ester is formed.

In the present paper this reaction has been extended to dinitrothymol, thymol, dinitrocarvacrol and nitro-*p*-cresotinic acid.* The first two like 4-chloro-2:6-dinitro-*m*-cresols give *p*-toluenesulphonyl esters in presence of diethylaniline as well as sodium carbonate. The esters obtained are very stable and are not converted into diphenylamine derivatives when heated with aniline.

The nitro-*p*-cresotinic acid used in the experiment has probably nitro group in the *ortho* position to OH as during nitration of the cresotic acid (Kostanecki and Niementoski, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 254; Einhorn and Pfl., *Annalen*, 1900, 311, 51), 2:6-dinitro-*p*-cresol (m. p. 82°) is formed, if the temperature is allowed to rise, the identity of which has been established by the preparation of the corresponding *p*-toluenesulphonyl ester, (m.p. 133°) (*cf.* Ullmann and Nadai, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1877).

The *p*-toluenesulphonyl compound of the ester of nitro-*p*-cresotinic acid is formed in presence of diethylaniline; it does not react with ammonia but unlike the corresponding compounds with dinitrocarvacrol and dinitrothymol, it gives diphenylamine derivative when boiled with aniline.

* Position 1 has been assigned to OH in cresols and hydroxy compounds and to COOH in cresotinic acids after the new edition of Beilstein (Vol. 6).

On hydrolysis this compound gives easily the free acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4: 6-Dinitrothymol-*p*-toluenesulphonate.—A mixture of dinitrothymol (8 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (6·5 g.) and diethylaniline (15 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for 4 hours. The cool mixture was then digested with dilute hydrochloric acid. The aqueous liquid was then decanted off and the liquid residue shaken with a little alcohol when it solidified. The ester dissolves easily in benzene and acetic acid, but is not easily soluble in alcohol. Colourless needles from acetic acid, m.p. 142°, yield 12 g. (Found: N, 7·02 ; S, 7·81, $C_{17}H_{18}O_7N_2S$ requires N, 7·1 ; S, 8·12 per cent.).

Dinitrothymol (4 g.) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (3·5 g.) were suspended in 20 c.c. of boiling water and sodium carbonate (3 g.) was added in small quantities at a time to the boiling mixture which was vigorously shaken during the reaction until the smell of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride disappeared. The cooled mixture was then filtered and the residue washed with sodium carbonate solution and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 142°. This ester is identical with the ester described above.

Dinitrocarvacrol-*p*-toluenesulphonate.—Dinitrocarvacrol (7 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (6·5 g.) and diethylaniline (15 c.c.) were heated together on the water-bath for 4 hours and the ester formed was obtained from it by the method already described. Colourless crystals from alcohol, m.p. 125°. The same ester is also obtained by using sodium carbonate as the condensing agent. (Found: N, 7·2 ; S, 8·23. $C_{17}H_{18}O_7N_2S$ requires N, 7·1 ; S, 8·12 per cent.).

Nitro-*p*-cresotinic acid.—Cresotinic acid (10 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (30 c.c.) and nitric acid (6 c.c. *d* 1·4) dissolved in an equal quantity of acetic acid, was added to the solution. After a short time the colour changed and the mixture became warm. The nitro compound was then precipitated by the addition of ice to the mixture; m.p. 173°.

When the nitration was not controlled by cooling the mixture, carboxyl group was displaced and 2: 6-dinitro-*p*-cresol (m.p. 82°) was formed. The *p*-toluenesulphonate of the latter melted at 153°.

p-Toluenesulphonate of 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylbenzoic acid ethyl ester.—Nitro-*p*-cresotinic acid ethyl ester, (m.p. 104-105°, 2 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2 g.) and diethylaniline (10 c.c.) were heated together on the water-bath and the toluenesulphonate separated as before. Colourless small plates from alcohol, m.p. 110°, yield 3 g. (Found: S, 8·27. $C_{17}H_{17}O_7NS$ requires S, 8·44 per cent.). Sodium carbonate was also used as condensing agent with the same result.

3-Methyl-5-nitro-6-diphenylamine benzoic acid ethyl ester.—*p*-Toluenesulphonate of nitrocresotinic acid ester (6 g.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (4 g.) were heated together with excess of aniline for some time. The excess of aniline was then removed by means of dilute HCl and the residue was crystallised from alcohol in yellowish needles, m. p. 136°. (Found: N, 9·26. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9·33 per cent.).

3-Methyl-5-nitro-6-diphenylamine benzoic acid.—The foregoing compound was dissolved in alcohol and hydrolysed by HCl. Brick red small rhombic crystals from alcohol, m.p. 174°. (Found: C, 61·52; H, 4·88; N, 10·4. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires C, 61·76; H, 4·41; N, 10·3 per cent.).

